

MEMO: Monitoring of Exotic MOsquitoes in Belgium

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Abstract

MEMO - Monitoring of Exotic MOSquitoes in Belgium is a sampling event dataset published by the Institute of Tropical Medicine in Antwerp (Belgium) (ITM). It is part of the early detection of exotic mosquito species (EMS) along high-risk introduction routes in Belgium, in which data are collected at defined locations (i.e. Points of Entry or PoE's) using a standardised protocol. The MEMO dataset contains mosquito sampling counts performed between 2017 and 2020, and the MEMO+2020, an extension of the MEMO dataset, contains only *Aedes albopictus* mosquito trap counts performed in 2020. Here, they are published as a standardised Darwin Core Archive, which includes for each sampling event an eventID, a date, a location and a sampling protocol (in the event core); and an occurrenceID for each occurrence (tube), the number of collected individuals per tube, species status (present/absent), information on the identification and scientific name (in the occurrence extension). Issues with the dataset can be reported at <https://github.com/BelgianBiodiversityPlatform/data-publication-ITG/issues>

Rationale

The early detection of exotic mosquito species (EMS), such as *Aedes albopictus*, *Aedes japonicus*, *Aedes koreicus* and *Aedes aegypti*, along high-risk introduction routes before populations become established is of paramount importance to prevent local transmission of mosquito-borne diseases. Following previous EMS surveillance projects in Belgium (Deblauwe et al. 2022), a three-year national active EMS monitoring project (MEMO) started in July 2017 to detect possible foci of introduction and establishment of EMS at an early stage in Belgium. The first phase of the project ran from 2017 till June-2020 (MEMO dataset) and the second phase from July till the end of November 2020 (MEMO+2020 dataset).

Figure 1: Overview of the MEMO Points of Entry (PoE's), with blue dots: MEMO; red diamonds: MEMO+2020. In total, 33 locations where sampled in Memo and 6 locations in Memo+2020

Datasets

MEMO (dataset 1)

In 2017, 2018 and 2019, active monitoring was implemented in 20 to 23 different PoE's (Figure 1). The risk of introduction and establishment of EMS at each PoE was re-evaluated annually to ensure that the monitoring focused on the highest risk sites. Different collection methods were

used, including BG-Sentinel, Mosquito Magnet® and gravid traps to collect host seeking female mosquitoes, oviposition traps to detect eggs, and larval sampling (Deblauwe et al. 2020). At each PoE a combination of different trapping methods was used simultaneously. The collected specimens were sorted and identified using morphological characteristics (Becker et al. 2010, Gunay et al. 2020, Pfitzner et al. 2018, Gillies & Coetzee 1987). The caught EMS and five percent of all collected mosquitoes were identified using DNA-based techniques to validate and confirm the morphological identification. Tissue and DNA were subsequently deposited in a molecular reference collection hosted at the Royal Belgian Institute of Natural Sciences (RBINS). A specific DNA-based identification [pipeline](#) was developed to enable the accurate identification to species (or biotype for *Culex pipiens* s.s.) level of all mosquitoes occurring in Belgium (native and potential EMS). Further, a morphological collection with a representation of 23 species and the most intact specimens sampled during the MEMO project was generated for future reference and is also hosted at RBINS. Data management was done using the VECMAP® software.

Figure 2: The morphological identifications and the number of individuals (grey) and the number of records (blue) in the MEMO dataset * **

*The majority of the specimens collected of the *Anopheles maculipennis* complex were molecularly identified up to species level. **Three adults could morphologically be identified as *Culex torrentium*, other specimens are grouped together with *Culex pipiens s.l.*

MEMO dataset 1: Monitoring of Exotic MOSquitoes in Belgium Source:

Original: <https://ipt.biodiversity.be/archive.do?r=itm-memo-occurrence>

GBIF: <https://www.gbif.org/dataset/a178c443-d737-4938-b983-5fa8e50936fe>

MEMO+2020 (dataset 2)

In 2020 active monitoring was implemented at six different PoE's (Figure 1). The focus was on parking lots along the highway as this import pathway for exotic *Aedes* species is becoming more and more important. Four fixed parking lots (Aische-en-Refail, Raeren, Marke, Saint-Ghislain) were monitored. Following the detections of *Ae. albopictus* in the Netherlands, two parking lots (Minderhout, Gierle) were added to the monitoring. Oviposition traps were used to collect eggs and potential breeding sites were inspected for larvae (Deblauwe et al. 2021). MEMO+2020 sampling resulted in one positive identification of *Ae. albopictus*.

MEMO+2020 dataset 2: Monitoring of Exotic MOSquitoes in Belgium Source:

Original: <https://ipt.biodiversity.be/archive.do?r=itm-memoplus-occurrence>

GBIF: <https://www.gbif.org/dataset/f5361e97-c8f1-4697-b209-8817e14ae780>

Keywords

Mosquito, surveillance, invasive *Aedes*, Points of Entry, introduction pathways, *Aedes albopictus*, *Aedes japonicus*, *Aedes koreicus*, Belgium, disease vectors

Taxonomic coverage of the two datasets

In the period 2000 - 2009 substantial changes were proposed for the Aedini Tribe taxonomy, which resulted in almost tripling the number of genera in the entire Culicidae family. A recent publication from Wilkerson et al. (2015) proposed a return to the taxonomy from before 2000, restoring a classification system useful for the operational community. This latter classification system was used during the MEMO and MEMO+2020 projects.

Sample processing for the two datasets

The adult specimens were killed by putting them at -20 °C upon arrival at the laboratory. Larvae were transported alive to the laboratory and killed by a thermal shock with hot water (70 °C). After the thermal shock, the larvae were transferred in 80 % ethanol for preservation before morphological identification. In the case of EMS, larvae were afterwards transferred in absolute ethanol for further DNA-based species validation. Morphological identification of adults and larvae was done with a stereomicroscope using dichotomic and digital keys (Becker et al. 2010, Gunay et al. 2020, Pfitzner et al. 2018, Gillies & Coetzee 1987). DNA-barcoding technology (Hebert et al. 2003) was applied to validate the morphological identification of EMS, of five percent of the annual sampling (quality control), and to identify damaged adults and larvae or species complexes (following the methodology of Smitz et al. 2021a). The step-by-step procedures can be viewed on the Github [MEMO repository](#).

The collected polystyrene pieces from oviposition traps were checked for the presence of EMS eggs in the laboratory by using a stereomicroscope. A subsample of the eggs from the polystyrene piece (1-5 eggs per side) was always DNA-barcoded (Smitz et al. 2021b). In 2020 the positive polystyrene pieces were immersed in water in secured containers, which were stored in a climate controlled cupboard. Hatched larvae (3rd or 4th instar) were stored in absolute ethanol for morphological identification. In case the eggs didn't hatch, DNA-barcoding was performed on the eggs for species identification.

The generated DNA barcodes were deposited on the open access GenBank sequence database (<https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/genbank/>), maintained by the National Center for Biotechnology

Information (NCBI). GenBank accession numbers to the generated barcodes are linked to the BioProject ID: PRJNA837425, or following <http://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/bioproject/837425> (Ibáñez-Justicia et al. 2020, De Wolf et al. 2021, Smitz et al. 2021a, Smitz et al. 2021b, Deblauwe et al. 2021). The generated microsatellites database for *Aedes japonicus* (population genetic investigation (Smitz et al. 2021b)) was deposited on the open-access Dryad Digital Repository (<https://doi.org/10.5061/dryad.p5hqbzkmw>).

Taxonomic ranks

Kingdom: *Animalia* **Class:** *Insecta* **Order:** *Diptera* **Family:** *Culicidae* **Subfamilies:** *Anophelinae* & *Culicinae*

Geographic coverage of the two datasets

Belgium is a small country in Western Europe. To the west, its 70 km coastline fronts the North Sea; to the north lies the Netherlands; to the east, Germany, and to the south, France and Luxembourg. Biogeographically, the fauna of eastern Belgium belongs to the Central European Province of the Eurasian (Palearctic), Continental Biogeographical Region region. By contrast, the rest of the country primarily consists of an Atlantic fauna (Atlantic Biogeographical Region) (Figure 3).

Figure 3: Biogeographical areas of Belgium

Politically and geographically, the country is divided into three parts: Flanders, Wallonia and the Brussels Capital Region. In Flanders (13, 522 km² and population of about 6 million people), to the north, soils are mainly sandy to loamy. The Brussels Capital Region is a small region (162 km²) entirely situated in the sandy loam area. In Wallonia (17, 006 km² and about 3, 5 million people), to the south, soils and habitats are more diverse, ranging from forests to rocky and calcareous grasslands on loam and chalky soils. Eastern Wallonia, near the German border, includes the Hautes Fagnes, a large area of bogs and peat.

Belgian has a temperate maritime climate that is influenced by the North Sea and the Atlantic Ocean with substantial precipitation in all seasons. The summer is moderate and the winters are mild.

Geographical method

All the selected sampling sites have exact GPS coordinates.

Bounding coordinates

50° to 51,51° latitude, 2,54° to 5,92° longitude.

Temporal coverage

The **MEMO dataset** (2017-08-17 – 2020-03-04), The **MEMO+2020 dataset** (2020-07-30 - 2020-27-11)

The overall distribution of the mosquito sampling events over time is illustrated in Figure 4.

Figure 4: Temporal coverage of the sampling effort.

Collection

The MEMO dataset (2017-2019), **The MEMO+2020 dataset** (2020)

Pinned adults and mounted larvae specimens are stored in the collections of the Royal Belgian Institute of Natural Sciences (Collection Identifier: IG32776; RBINS: IG34179). The extracted DNA was dried for long-term storage at room temperature, using the GenTegra®-DNA technology. All samples which were used for molecular identification are stored in 2D SmartScan™ boxes at -80 °C (ABgene™), each tube being equipped with a unique eight digit code. These codes are linked to the occurrenceID and eventID in the MEMO and MEMO+2020 datasets.

Method step description:

1. Researchers from ITM defined the appropriate sampling protocol for the target EMS species.
2. Fieldwork was planned and coordinated by ITM.
3. Data was collected in the field by specialised personnel.
4. The collected data was entered into VecMap.
5. The data was exported and manually corrected by experts.
6. A custom R & Grel (General Refine Expression Language) script was created to map the original data to Darwin Core as an event core with an occurrence extension. (<https://github.com/BelgianBiodiversityPlatform/data-publication-ITG>).
7. The Darwin Core files are connected to the BBPF IPT and documented with metadata.
8. The datasets are published and registered with GBIF.

Dataset description

The occurrence data from the MEMO (dataset 1) and MEMO+2020 (dataset 2) projects are extracted, standardised, and published as two separate Darwin Core Archives:

The Darwin Core terms (<http://rs.tdwg.org/dwc/terms/>) in the dataset at the time of publication are:

MEMO & MEMO+2020 datasets

Darwin Core terms used in both datasets:

Event Core

id; eventID; type; language; license; rightsHolder; accessRights; datasetID; institutionCode; datasetName; parentEventID; samplingProtocol; eventDate; habitat; locationID; continent; countryCode; municipality; locality; decimalLatitude; decimalLongitude; coordinateUncertaintyInMeters; geodeticDatum

Occurrence Extension

id; eventID; collectionCode; basisOfRecord; materialSampleID; occurrenceID; recordedBy; individualCount; sex; lifeStage; establishmentMeans; occurrenceStatus; identifiedBy; dateIdentified; identificationRemarks; scientificName; kingdom; taxonRank; nomenclaturalCode

- Object name: Darwin Core Archive MEMO+2020 - Monitoring Exotic MOSquitoes in Belgium
 - DOI: <https://doi.org/10.15468/r42fr7>
 - Character encoding: UTF-8
 - Format name: Darwin Core Archive format
 - Format version: 1.0
 - Distribution: <https://ipt.biodiversity.be/archive.do?r=itm-memoplus-occurrence>
 - Publication date of data: 2021-11-03
 - Language: English
 - Licences of use: <https://creativecommons.org/publicdomain/zero/1.0/>
 - Metadata language: English
 - Date of metadata creation: 2021-08-24
 - Hierarchy level: Dataset
-
- Object name: Darwin Core Archive MEMO-Monitoring Exotic MOSquitoes in Belgium
 - DOI: <https://doi.org/10.15468/4u5aub>
 - Character encoding: UTF-8
 - Format name: Darwin Core Archive format
 - Format version: 1.0
 - Distribution: <https://ipt.biodiversity.be/archive.do?r=itm-memo-occurrence>
 - Publication date of data: 2021-11-09
 - Language: English
 - Licences of use: <https://creativecommons.org/publicdomain/zero/1.0/>
 - Metadata language: English

- Date of metadata creation: 2021-08-24
- Hierarchy level: Dataset

The data are published under a Creative Commons CC0 waiver and we kindly ask you to notify the corresponding authors of the respective dataset if you use the data, especially for research purposes.

Additional information

This data paper is linked with two MEMO related datasets; (1) the dataset 1, (2) the dataset 2. The database server uses Windows Server 2003 SBS R2 as operating system, and is running IIS with PHP for site development, MS SQL Server for database development and SQL Server Mobile Tools to allow remote access from a PDA.

Project data

Project title: Monitoring of Exotic MOsquitoes in Belgium

The MEMO and MEMO+2020 projects (2017 – 2020) were financed by the Flemish, Walloon and Brussels regional governments and the Federal Public Service (FPS) Public Health, Food Chain Safety and Environment in the context of the National Environment and Health Action Plan (NEHAP) (Belgium),

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